

THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIAL COHESION IN THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CIVIL SOCIETY

Rakhmatullaev Alimjon Riskulovich

PhD, Senior Lecturer, Almalyk branch of Tashkent State Polytechnic University, UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article reveals the importance of the social aspect in the formation and development of civil society, as well as its main aspects and factors.

In the conditions of general globalization, modernization, and democratization processes, civil society gained independent power and became a leading and decisive force in the evolutionary process. New trends have emerged in the relations between the state and society. They have a more dynamic and interrelated nature and have approached the vital interests of each of the participants. In turn, social cohesion, from our point of view, clearly ensures the quality of the process of forming a modern civil society, which can change society, resist destruction, crisis, decline, eliminate violent conflicts, and contribute to the stability of society. , based on contributing to its improvement and strengthening [2].

Social cohesion, which implies social integration, maintaining order in society, ensuring social and national harmony, and preventing the masses from moving away from power, is the result of the maturity of civil society, the quality content of the process of the formation of civil society.

However, the development and determination of civil society shows that in the interest of having reliable scientific knowledge, it is not the question of whether civil society occurred or not, but to what extent or development of civil society. It is useful to ask the question of how important it is [1]. Civil society is a self-producing place of social justice and a community of solidarity, so where should we look for the potential for cohesion in civil society and how to mobilize this potential [3]? It should be said that the nature of the era, its specific cultural-spiritual, ideological, and technological spaces, and the status of social subjects determine the given nature and model the essence of social changes. First of all, we are interested in the process of qualitative transition from the traditional forms of existence of society (industrial society) to the developed civil society in the new postmodern conditions, which is an urgent problem both directly in the society of Uzbekistan and directly as a society in the aspect of global problems.

Answering the question of what causes underdeveloped social solidarity in today's modern society, we face several problems that fundamentally prevent the optimization of the social system and prevent the deeper opening of the internal potential of society [3]. One of these problems is increasing social isolation in an individualistic and morally flawed post-industrial society.

"In the social sphere, the importance of diversity in the establishment and development of civil society also corresponds to mass media, whose main characteristics seem amorphous, blurred, and unclear. There is no clearly defined social class structure. The level of consumption - mainly material - is the main criterion for dividing into social strata. It is a society of universal conformity and compromise. It becomes more and more difficult to apply the concept of "people" to them because the latter is increasingly becoming a faceless "electorate", an amorphous mass of "consumers" and "customers" ... Postmodern man ... about tomorrow and even the distant future live one day at a time without worrying too much about it. The main incentive for him is professional and financial success. Moreover, this success should be as early as possible, not late in life. For this, even in the development of civil society, the individual is ready to sacrifice any principles... the worldview of the modern person lacks strong enough support because all forms of ideology seem vague and uncertain... this worldview can be described... a person no longer understands himself as the master of his destiny... He realizes that too much in his life depends on chance, the game of luck ... The importance of unity is also losing" [4].

The common ideological, mental, and cultural space here is a mosaic, therefore, social transformation is not represented here by transpersonal subjects (classes, nations, etc.), on the contrary, on the one hand, individuals and their free associations are also given a dimension. on the other hand, it is determined by the systematic and organizational processes of the technical, technological, and information plan. The most obvious manifestations of socio-subjective differences are "elite (political, primarily) and society", "intellectuals are the faces of popular culture" and others [2]. In modern international society, the principle of the mechanism of changing society through subjective transformations in the world reveals the semantic, communicative, and constructive features of the subject [1]. We can note that today, in the process of forming civil society, it is of particular importance to reconsider the integrity of society and to "recode" it through ideological, semantic, and value parameters. This is a change in the way society is socially manifested for contemporaries, a reassessment of the most important means of life support, and so on.

Based on the research carried out by local and foreign scientists, it can be noted that the importance of the social aspect is a broad concept, and its content can be interpreted from the point of view of both labor relations and beneficial relations between state and civil society institutions. In the narrow sense, it is considered a form of concrete relations between the social and civil society institutions. In a broad sense, it is a mutual special partnership of social groups, regardless of the object aimed at conducting such relations, that is, not only in social relations but also in other areas, including the interaction of state and civil society institutions. improvement of legislation aimed at strengthening cooperation, implementation

of socio-economic programs, and state and non-state organizations commonality of interests in a single field is also understood [1].

In general, today our country is living with the high goals of forming a legal democratic state and a civil society based on it. The formation of national statehood, new economic relations, and the formation of the legal system have become the decisive basis of our independent development. At the same time, the path we have traveled shows the tasks that must be solved today to achieve the goals of our country.

First of all, the formation of the spirit of a free civil society, in other words, a free, well-recognized people who know their rights, who believe in self-sufficiency, who live by their strength and intelligence, and who at the same time take care of their interests, is to educate perfect people who see the interests of the country in harmony with the interests of the country"[4]. Therefore, bringing up the young generation, who are the successors of the development of our society, to maturity both physically and mentally, has become an urgent problem of today. So, it is a vital necessity that Uzbekistan has chosen a unique and appropriate way to build a democratic civil society, and this work cannot be done without morally renewing the society and raising a new generation.

It is necessary to realize that the development of theories, ideas, thoughts, and opinions based on the scientific point of view, fully compatible with the requirements of the modern state and society, and our national interests, is the demand of the times.

Thirdly, non-governmental non-commercial organizations are involved in the moral development of society, the application of legal democratic principles in all spheres of society, and the formation of civil society. activity is particularly important. After all, as political scientist-scientist Habermas noted: "... one of the unique features of civil society is voluntary membership in all state and non-state public organizations in the system of its institutions. This rule, firstly, shows a high level of democracy in the society, and secondly, it means that the social consciousness and activities of the members of the society are high" [2].

Fourth, the old-fashioned way of thinking, and outdated thinking stereotypes are serious problems in the way of modernizing our country and building a strong civil society. Getting rid of these thought patterns is one of the important factors ensuring the success of our reforms.

Fifth, establishing a civil society based on Eastern democracy in Uzbekistan is one of the main goals of our country's development. In this sense, eastern democracy means a peaceful resolution of any controversial issues, free exchange of ideas, reaching a conclusion that represents the interests of all citizens, eliminating any ideological pressures based on the superstitions and reasoning of the peoples of the East, which have been formed over the centuries. is to ensure a free and prosperous life.

Sixth, institutions of civil society have a deep symbolic meaning as a constantly repeating, organizing tool of the mutual relations between the state and society, and their specific normative rules. In other words, civil society institutions are also symbolic and legal indicators of the development of the national, spiritual, legal, socio-political, and economic spheres of society.

Based on the above, it can be said that from the social aspect, the state and civil society institutions are completely objectively interested, because it achieves the socio-political stability of the society, its development, and socio-economic development, which is the basis for achieving the highest level of civil society formation. creates. In particular, the result of consistent reforms in the field of development of state and civil society institutions, and measures aimed at improving the legal framework, is the most important guarantee of the formation of a legal democratic state and a strong civil society.

Thus, we find that each era develops its own "models" of qualitative changes in society - models that justify the means of such changes from the modern era - based on their goals, common "technologies" - a set of "algorithms" This process has been carried out in terms of the importance of the international community and its development. But in this regard, the role of the subject and the place of unity in the process of building social changes do not change: its importance and characteristics mainly determine the specific characteristics of changes and the process of civil society formation. The content and inseparable features of the quality are the social movement aimed at changing the institutional possibilities that represent the values, interests, and goals of the international society, and as a sign and source of unity, it is an indicator of modern society and its harmony. shows the level of unity, integration, orderliness; stability, and endurance, based on determination to provide for one's own needs.

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